

One Nation, One Election: Opportunities and Challenges

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Introduction:

“One nation, one election recently passed by government of India has attracted a lot of discussions all over India. This attempt has been proposed after consulting the report of a taskforce headed by former president of India, Ramnath Kovind and intended to co-ordinate the Lok Sabha, State Legislative Assemblies, Municipalities and Panchayats. For its supporters the change will increase administrative effectiveness and decrease costs of elections, whereas critics express more focuses on the impacts on democracy and federalism.

Objectives of Research Paper:

1. Study of opportunities and obstacles or challenges of the one nation, one election bill.

Research Method:

The present research paper has been compiled using secondary source for study eg. Newspaper, previous research articles.

Content Analysis:

During the first four general election cycles in 1952, 1957, 1962 and 1967, the elections to the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies were hold simultaneously. How ever, due to the subsequent premature dissolution of the Lok Sabha on seven occasions and the premature dissolution of legislative assemblies on various occasions. The election to the Lok Sabha

and Various state assemblies are held at different times. In 2019 only four states had their assembly elections, along with the Lok Sabha the idea of simultaneous elections has been mooted in the past by the Election Commission of India (1982) and The Law commission (1999).

Opportunities and Challenges:

- If “one nation, one election” is implemented, the biggest advantage will be a reduction in election expenses. Conducting elections simultaneously will reduce costs incurred on multiple elections.
- According to reports, the 2019 elections alone cost around 60,000 CR. Another benefit is that administrative officials, staff and security forces will have a reduced workload due to a single election, allowing them to focus more on their regular duties. Additionally simultaneous elections will help maintain continuity in the implementation of central and state governments schemes.
- Constitutional and Legal hurdles in executing the one nation, one election bill. In that we see Indian democracy runs on federal structure where the centre and state operate independently so synchronizing elections would demand a massive constitutional overall. The government would need to dissolve all State assemblies where each of them have a

different tenure and we have to align them with the Lok Sabha election and for this work of government would need to rewrite at least five constitutional articles which are article 83, 85, 172, 174 and article 356.

- The second challenge is overlapping national and state issues in that case India is a patchwork of diverse state cultures and issues and yet under one nation, one election. National narratives might just overshadow regional voices. Infact when elections are synchronized study shows that 77% chance that the voter would choose the same party for both centre and state. Lastly third is the frequent election, even though costly, ensures that government remain accountable to the people throughout their term.

Conclusion:

The policy one nation, one election provides an interesting chance to change the electoral system of India. Thus the benefits of cost efficiency, administrative convenient and enhanced governance cannot be dismissed while considering the drawback of this concept. however, the proposed amendments the pilot approach, effective voter's education, use of technology are critical for the implementation of the strategy.

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